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Development of high strength Al alloys processable by SLM for aeronautic application: analysis and comparative study

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Abstract

Conventionally processed aluminium alloys (i.e., those in the 2xxx/6xxx/7xxx series) are currently used in the aerospace sector due to their capabilities of withstanding extreme conditions. Additive manufacturing produces complex net-shape and light-weight parts, with high versatility on design and improved functionalities, which is extremely attractive to the aerospace industry. Thermal characteristics in the selective laser melting (SLM) process are critical for high-strength aluminium alloys because they are susceptible to hot tearing and hot cracking, also during conventional processing.

On the contrary, the currently SLM-processable aluminium alloys (i.e., AlSi10Mg) do not meet the mechanical requirements for aeronautical applications.

In this work, the development of different high strength Al alloys processable for SLM is described. Two approaches have been taken: (1) to improve the mechanical properties of currently processable aluminium alloys; (2) to avoid hot cracking of conventional aluminium alloys by modifying chemical composition. The analysis of each alloy and a comparative study have been performed.

1. Introduction

Currently there are only a few Al alloys suitable to be processed by SLM. The most commonly alloys used in this technology are the AlSi10Mg, AlSi12 and Scalmalloy® alloys. Thus, it is crucial to search for alternative alloys to be processed in order to broaden the range of materials to be applied. In addition, the lack of high-strength Al alloys is very detrimental mainly to the aeronautical application where the lightweighting of components is a key factor as well as the achievement of specific mechanical properties, such as fatigue strength, tensile strength and so on.

Aluminium alloys, such as those in the 2xxx, 6xxx and 7xxx series, are currently used in the aerospace sector for demanding applications due to their capabilities of withstanding extreme stress, temperature and pressure variations with strict quality requirements [1]. Nowadays, these aluminium alloys are processed by conventional subtractive processes like machining operations. In contrast to traditional subtractive manufacturing, additive manufacturing technologies can produce complex net-shape parts with improved designs that make light-weight structures and new functions feasible. All these characteristics are extremely attractive to the aerospace industry. However, SLM processing has limitations related to the high thermal gradients during manufacturing. Moreover, thermal characteristics of SLM processing are particularly critical for high-strength 2xxx, 6xxx and 7xxx series [2] aluminium alloys, because these alloys are susceptible to hot tearing and hot cracking, also during conventional processing, i.e. in casting and welding processes [3][4].

On the other hand, the currently SLM-processable aluminium alloys, such as AlSi10Mg and AlSi12, do not meet the requirements in terms of mechanical properties for aeronautical applications. The Scalmalloy® alloy is an Al-Mg-Sc-Zr alloy, which was developed by Airbus Group Corporate Research Center (Airbus Group Innovations) [5] over the last ten years, based on 5xxx series. It was specifically developed for additive manufacturing and it can be applied in the SLM technology. However, the use of this alloy has been limited to only one supplier until now and the application of Sc significantly raises the cost of the powder. Thus, other alloy designs need to be developed to achieve high strength and processability by the SLM technology, with competitive prices and with mechanical properties meeting aeronautical requirements.

The aim of this work was to develop different high strength Al alloys processable by SLM for aeronautic applications. These materials were developed and different approaches were taken. The first approach was intended to improve the mechanical properties of currently SLM-processable AlSi10Mg alloy by adding Cu, while the second approach aimed to avoid hot cracking of the

conventional aluminium alloy Al7075 also by modifying chemical composition. Both materials were characterized and compared with the conventional alloys (AlSi10Mg and Al7075).

2. Materials and methods

Two different materials were applied: AlSi10Mg/Cu and Al7075/Zr. Both powders were gas atomized and provided by IMDEA Materials Institute (Spain) within the collaboration in the framework of the ALFORAMA project (CS2, Funded under: H2020-EU.3.4.5.2). The particle size distribution was between 20-63 μm . The behaviour of AlSi10Mg/Cu powder was compared with that of commercially available AlSi10Mg, which was provided by SLM Solutions, and the behaviour of Al7075/Zr was compared with that of commercially available Al7075, which was produced by TLS Technik Spezialpulver. The chemical compositions of commercially available AlSi10Mg and Al7075 powders are given in Table 1. Their morphologies and microstructures were observed by a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM Ultra Plus, Zeiss). Keller's reagent was used to etch the Al7075/Zr powder. Cubes ($10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$) were manufactured with all powders, employing the optimum processing parameters determined previously with the aim to obtain parts with minimum porosity, free of defects and superior surface quality. These parts were built in a SLM machine developed by Renishaw (AM 400 system). The Reduced Build Volume (RBV) platform was employed. This machine is equipped with 400 W fiber laser and works with a protective atmosphere containing 0.1 % maximum oxygen during manufacturing. The as-built samples were cross-sectioned and polished. Afterwards, these samples were characterized by Optical microscopy (GX51 Olympus) and the FE-SEM. Relative density was determined by optical microscope (GX51 Olympus) and using the AnalySIS document image analysis software. Hardness measurements were carried out in Emco Test DuraScan durometer. An X-Ray diffractometer (RIGAKU, "D-Max/2500") with a rotary anode was employed to unambiguously identify and quantify existing phases in the AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy. This machine operated at 40 KV and 80 mA with Cu anode employing a step size of 0.03° and scanning speed of 1 sec/step in a 2θ range of $10\text{--}80^\circ$. The AlSi10Mg/Cu powder was subjected to different heat treatments: solution heat treatment (SHT) at 470°C for 2 h and subsequent ageing at 180°C for 12 h and only ageing at 180°C for 12 h.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of commercial AlSi10Mg and Al7075 powders.

	Al	Si	Mg	Fe	Cu	Mn	Cr	Ni	Zn	Pb	Sn	Ti	O
AlSi10Mg	Bal.	9.94	0.38	0.16	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.02	0.04
Al7075	Bal.	0.25	2.46	0.097	1.40	0.12	0.23	-	5.63	-	-	-	-

3. Results and discussion

As it is explained at the Introduction, two approaches were taken to obtain innovative high strength Al alloys processable by the SLM technology. This work summarizes the results achieved from these two pre-alloyed powders: AlSi10Mg/Cu and Al7075/Zr. The aim of using the AlSi10Mg/Cu powder was to improve the mechanical properties of the currently widely processed AlSi10Mg alloy to meet the requirements of the aeronautic industry, while the goal of using the Al7075/Zr powder was to improve the processability of the currently used wrought Al7075 alloy by avoiding or reducing the hot cracking susceptibility during SLM.

3.1. Powder characterization

3.1.1. AlSi10Mg/Cu

The AlSi10Mg/Cu pre-alloyed powder was characterized in terms of flowability, microstructure and morphology. This powder presents a spherical morphology with some satellites and a few irregular particles (spheroidicity: 79 %) (Figure 1a). The internal porosity of the powder is 0.015 % (Figure 1b). The powder shows a humidity below 10 % and continuous flow. The particle size distribution is shown in Figure 1c. The values of D10, D50 and D90 are 32 μm , 52 μm and 69 μm , respectively, which means that 10 %, 50 % and 90 % of the volume have particles with sizes below these values. Analysing polished powder at higher magnifications, it can be observed that the pre-alloyed powder

exhibits Cu-rich segregation occurred during the atomization process (Figure 2) which makes the microstructure different from that of the conventional AISi10Mg powder.

Figure 1. AISi10Mg/Cu powder (a) morphology, (b) polished powder showing internal porosity and (c) particle size distribution.

Figure 2. AISi10Mg/Cu polished powder showing Cu-rich segregation (white).

3.1.2. Al7075/Zr

The Al7075/Zr pre-alloyed powder was characterized in the same way as the AISi10Mg/Cu powder. This powder presents an elongated morphology with some satellites (sphericity: 39 %) (Figure 3a). Some powder particles show attached particles on the surface which are Zn-rich. The internal porosity of the powder is 0.19 %. In spite of the presence of irregular particles, the powder shows a humidity below 10 % and continuous flow. The particle size distribution is shown in Figure 3c. The values of D10, D50 and D90 are 41 μm, 60 μm and 76 μm, respectively. After etching with Keller’s reagent, the internal microstructure of the powder was revealed, showing the grains and splat caps formed during the cooling phase of the atomization process.

Figure 3. Al7075/Zr powder (a) morphology, (b) etched polished powder showing internal microstructure and (c) particle size distribution.

3.2. As-built sample characterization

3.2.1. AlSi10Mg/Cu

The as-built sample show a fine cellular-dendritic solidification microstructure very similar to that of AlSi10Mg alloy [6] but exhibit differences in composition. The matrix (grey phase, Figure 4b,c) is rich in aluminium, while the cells (white phase, Figure 4b,c) are rich in Si in some areas and rich in Cu in others. In addition, unlike the AlSi10Mg alloy, these innovative alloys contain the CuAl_2 strengthening phase as it was detected by DRX (Figure 4d).

Figure 4. As-built sample microstructure (a-c) and (d) X-Ray Diffraction pattern showing CuAl_2 precipitates.

3.2.2. Al7075/Zr

The same optimized process parameters (hatch space, power, thickness layer and scan speed) were employed in producing the conventional Al7075 alloy and Al7075/Zr powders to minimize the crack density, when processing by SLM. It is observed that the addition of Zr significantly decreases the cracking density (Figure 5, top) as well as refines the microstructure in comparison with the conventionally processed Al7075 alloy (Figure 5, bottom). This is because the Zr addition allows the precipitation of the Al_3Zr phase, which is formed at low-energy heterogeneous nucleation sites. This induces a fine equiaxed structure, as it was explained by other researchers [7]. In addition, the addition of Zr does not affect the solidification behaviour of the Al7075 alloy, which confirms that the reason for the reduction of cracking is mainly due to the presence of Al_3Zr nucleants.

Figure 5. Optical micrographs of the as-built samples of Al7075 conventional alloy (Left) and Al7075/Zr alloy (right) before (top) and after (bottom) etching with Keller's reagent.

3.3. Heat treatments

It is well known that the AlSi10Mg alloy improves its mechanical properties by heat treatments, since the precipitation of the Mg_2Si hardening phase is promoted. In the case of the AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy, the heat treatment is expected to increase the content of $CuAl_2$ precipitates. The typical T6 heat treatment (SHT 450 °C + ageing 180 °C) was carried out as well as only ageing at 180 °C. X-Ray diffraction of the AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy in the as-built state and after these heat treatments revealed that the $CuAl_2$ content is higher after the ageing heat treatment without the solution heat treatment. The Mg_2Si phase was not detected probably because there was no sufficient quantity to allow identification. The peak-aged condition was detected at 180 °C after 4 h. The improvement of these heat treatments needs to be performed to fully take advantage of the $CuAl_2$ phase precipitation.

Table 2. $CuAl_2$ phase content in each stage of AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy measured by X-ray diffraction.

Phase (wt.%)	As-built	Only ageing	SHT 450 C + ageing
$CuAl_2$	3,03	3,98	1,77

T6 is the typical heat treatment, which is applied also to the conventional Al7075 alloy. The optimization of the heat treatment for the Al7075/Zr alloy processed by SLM needs to be performed.

3.4. Comparison between mechanical properties of conventional and modified alloys

The comparison in microhardness between the SLM processed conventional and modified alloys is shown in Figure 6. The addition of Cu and Zr alloying elements to the conventional SLM processed AlSi10Mg and Al7075 alloys, respectively, improves the mechanical properties. The ageing heat treatment of AlSi10Mg and AlSi10Mg/Cu promotes precipitation hardening. Cu addition increases the hardness until 176 $HV_{0.5}$ in the peak-aged condition, which is a hardness achieved by the wrought Al7075 alloy after the T6 treatment. Thus, the improvement of the mechanical properties of AlSi10Mg by Cu addition to the Al7075 level is proven. On the other hand, Al7075 processed by SLM shows high quantity of cracks. The addition of Zr significantly reduces the cracking susceptibility and increases the hardness value. It is expected that the application of optimized heat treatment to this

alloy would promote $MgZn_2$ and Al_3Zr precipitation and, consequently, the hardness would significantly improve.

Figure 6. Comparison in microhardness between all samples processed by SLM and wrought Al7075 before and after the T6 heat treatment. AB: As-built; HT: Heat treated; PA: Peak-aged condition.* Al7075 as-built showed a large number of cracks and the value could be not too accurate.

4. Conclusions

Two new high strength aluminium alloys to be processed by SLM were successfully developed: AlSi10Mg/Cu and Al7075/Zr. The AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy achieved a hardness in the range of the conventionally used Al7075 wrought material due to $CuAl_2$ precipitation during ageing heat treatment. Thus, the AlSi10Mg/Cu alloy has the potential to be applied in the aeronautical industry due to the improvement in mechanical properties. On the other hand, the processability of the conventional Al7075 powder by SLM was significantly improved by adding the Zr alloying element. This addition reduced the cracking susceptibility due to the precipitation of the Al_3Zr phase, which acts as heterogeneous nucleation sites and refines the microstructure. An improvement in the mechanical properties of the Al7075/Zr alloy is expected when an optimized heat treatment is applied. Thus, the Al7075/Zr alloy will be successfully processed by SLM and exhibit mechanical properties similar to or better than the wrought Al7075 after the T6 heat treatment. All these achievements will have a high impact on the aeronautic sector as the range of available high-strength aluminium alloys will be broadened, thereby avoiding material limitations.

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References

- [1] C. S. Jawalkar and S. Kant, "A Review on use of aluminium alloys in aircraft components," *Journal on Material Science*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 33–38, 2018.
- [2] M. L. Montero Sistiaga *et al.*, "Changing the alloy composition of Al7075 for better processability by selective laser melting," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 238, pp. 437–445, 2016.
- [3] P. Kikani and H. R. Thakkar, "Study of cracking susceptibility in Al alloys welds," *2nd International Conference on emerging Trends in Mechanical Engineering*, no. 1, pp. 50–55, 2017.
- [4] P. Kah, E. Hiltunen, J. Martikainen, and W. Gedik, "Investigation of hot cracking in the welding of aluminium alloys (6005 & 6082)," *International Conference on Advances in Welding Science and Technology for Construction, Energy and Transportation, AWST 2010, held in Conjunction with the 63rd Annual Assembly of the International Institute of Welding, IIW 2010*, no. October, pp. 373–380, 2010.
- [5] "https://www.apworks.de/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/1707711_AIRBUS-APWORKS-SCALMALLOY_Overview.pdf."
- [6] A. Iturrioz, E. Gil, M. M. Petite, F. Garciandia, A. M. Mancisidor, and M. San Sebastian, "Selective laser melting of AlSi10Mg alloy: influence of heat treatment condition on mechanical properties and microstructure," *Welding in the World*, vol. 65, pp. 417–424, Apr. 2018.

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- [7] J. H. Martin, B. D. Yahata, J. M. Hundley, J. A. Mayer, T. A. Schaedler, and T. M. Pollock, "3D printing of high-strength aluminium alloys," *Nature*, vol. 549, no. 7672, pp. 365–369, 2017.